

Behaviour of Sodium Diethyldithiocarbamate in Non-aqueous Solvents

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Sodium diethyldithiocarbamate is a diacidic base. The two groups of the substance can be differentiated by titrating it in (i) acetic anhydride and (ii) acetic acid as solvents. The titration of the substance in (i) reveals the first break while that in (ii) reveals an overall jump, corresponding to the utilisation of two equivalents of HClO_4 in *p*-dioxane. This procedure can be applied for the estimation of the substance.

It has been shown previously (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 349) that sodium diethyldithiocarbamate is a diacidic base in water, the two dissociation constants of the corresponding acid being $\text{p}k_1 = 7.5$ and $\text{p}k_2 = 8.4$. In the present investigation the behaviour of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate in non-aqueous solvents has been studied. It has now been found that with acetic anhydride as a solvent, it is possible to obtain the first jump clearly while the second jump alone is obtained in solvents like acetic acid, ethanol, etc.

EXPERIMENTAL

A known quantity of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (B.D.H., A.R.) was dissolved either in different solvents or their mixture and titrated against HClO_4 in acetic acid or *p*-dioxane. Chemicals used were either of B.D.H., A.R. or of Reagent grade. As the commercial *p*-dioxane gave a faint blue colour with HClO_4 , *p*-dioxane of A.R., B.D.H. quality was used. Acetic anhydride was distilled before use.

The end point of the reaction was detected potentiometrically using pH meter equipped with glass and calomel electrodes. HClO_4 in *p*-dioxane or acetic acid was standardised by titrating it against a weighed quantity of sodium bicarbonate in glacial acetic acid.

DISCUSSION

Curves 1 and 2 (Fig. 1) show the nature of the curve when 0.10 g. of the substance was dissolved in 25 c.c. of acetic acid and titrated against 0.104*N*- HClO_4 in acetic acid and 0.0682*N*- HClO_4 in *p*-dioxane respectively. A clear jump is observed at the utilisation of two equivalents of the titrant acid, showing diacidity of the substance. This is in agreement with our previous findings (*loc. cit.*). The neutralisation of the substance at two equivalents was found to be independent of concentration of the substance or of the solvent. The neutralisation at two equivalents was also observed when ethanol and nitrobenzene were used as solvents. In case of nitrobenzene, it is necessary to add a little acetic acid to dissolve the substance.

The mixed solvents are sometimes better than a single solvent as the colour changes of the indicators or potentiometric breaks are sharpened. Fig. 2 apparently shows that the end point is sharpened as the dielectric constant of the medium is decreased (Pifer and Wollish, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, **24**, 300). Thus a mixture of *p*-dioxane-acetic acid (curve 3) is better than a mixture of chloroform-acetic acid (curve 2), which is better than acetic acid (curve 1). It is not possible, however, to use dioxane alone as a solvent as too low a dielectric constant results in unsteady potentials. Chloroform being an aprotic solvent tends to depress solvolysis and provides fairly sharp end points (Pifer *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, **25**, 310).

FIG. 1

Curve No.	Scale axis. X. Y.	Reagent.	AcOH.	Ac ₂ O.	CHCl ₃ .	Titrant. (HClO ₄).	End point.				
							Calc.	Obs.			
1.	2 c.c.	50mv	0.1 g.	25c.c.	..	0.1044N in AcOH	..	8.5	..	8.5	
2.	2	50	0.1	25	..	0.0882N in <i>p</i> -dioxane	..	10.07	..	10.1	
3.	2	100	0.1	..	5c.c.	50c.c.	0.116N in <i>p</i> -dioxane	3.85	7.7	3.8	6.8

In the present investigation, we tried to differentiate the two basic groups of the substance. Acetonitrile was found the best to differentiate amines having pK 's nearer to each other (Fritz, *ibid.*, 1953, **25**, 407). It was inapplicable in the present case, as the substance was found insoluble in acetonitrile. Intitrating certain weak amines, the water should be removed as much as possible by

titrating in a mixture containing acetic anhydride (Fritz and Fulda, *ibid.*, 1953, 25, 1837). When the above procedure was applied to the present case, it was found that the first neutralisation jump at the utilisation of one equivalent of the acid was clear.

FIG. 2

Curve No.	Scale axis		Reagent	AcOH	<i>p</i> -Dioxane	CHCl ₃	Titrant (HClO ₄)	End point			
	X	Y						Calc.	Obs.		
1.	2 c.c.	50mv	0.1 g.	55c.c.	..	..	0.113 N in <i>p</i> -dioxane.	..	7.9	..	7.9
2.	2	50	0.1	5	..	50c.c.	..	..	7.9	..	7.9
3.	2	50	0.1	5	50c.c.	..	..	..	7.9	..	7.8

Table I records the results of several experiments in different solvents. Table I shows that the first break at one equivalent is obtained in all the cases when acetic anhydride is used as a component of the solvent mixture; but the serious disadvantage of this solvent is the shifting of the second jump (see No. 1 to 6, 8 and 9).

TABLE I

In all experiments 0.10 g. of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate was taken.

No.	AcOH.	Ac ₂ O.	CHCl ₃ .	Aceto- nitrile.	Nitro- benzene.	Titrant HClO ₄ in dioxane.	End points.			
							Calc.		Obs.	
							I.	II.	I.	II.
1.	..	50 c.c.	..	..	..	0.113N	3.95	7.9	4.0	7.2
2.	..	10	100 c.c.	..	..	0.110	4.05	8.1	4.05	7.6
3.	*10 c.c.	10	100	..	..	0.110	4.05	8.1	4.0	7.7
4.	..	5	50	..	..	0.116	3.85	7.7	3.80	6.8
5.	5	5	100	..	..	0.088	5.04	10.08	5.0	8.5
6.	..	5	..	..	50 c.c.	0.116	3.85	7.7	3.8	6.9
7.	5	..	..	..	50	0.116	3.85	7.7	..	7.8
8.	..	10	..	20 c.c.	..	0.104	4.25	8.5	4.3	7.5
9.	..	5	50	20	..	0.104	4.25	8.5	4.25	9.0
10.	5	..	50	20	..	0.110	4.02	8.05	..	8.0

* Acetic acid (10 c.c.) added after first neutralisation.

The addition of acetic anhydride increases the dielectric constant of the medium; it also removes water from the system, thereby sharpening the end point. Mere shifting of the dielectric constant of the medium is not enough to obtain the first jump, as titrations carried out with mixtures (of different solvents) having nearly the same dielectric constant did not provide the first jump although the second or overall jump was observed. On the other hand, in the presence of acetic anhydride the second jump is shifted, which may be partly due to the change in dielectric constant of the medium and partly to the possibility of acetylation of the secondary amine, which may have been formed in the reaction.

In acetic acid medium the substance consumes exactly two equivalents of the acid and in presence of acetic anhydride, the first jump is exactly at the utilisation of one equivalent of the acid. Application of this procedure can differentiate the two groups.

Estimation of the Substance.—Dithiocarbamates may be estimated by direct titration with a standard iodine solution (Lieber *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1932, 4, 98); alternatively gravimetric estimation of sulphur has been suggested (Linch, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 293). Both the methods are, however, liable to errors.

The present work suggests a neat method of estimating the substance by titrating it (dissolved in acetic acid) against perchloric acid in *p*-dioxane, when both the groups are estimated. On the other hand, using adequate proportion of acetic anhydride as one of the components of the solvent mixture, the first group is estimated. Thus estimation may be checked by two independent methods. The presence of basic impurities will interfere with the estimation. The fact that the titre value for the overall jump is double the titre value of the first jump, indicates that such impurities may not be present.

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